

MAIN PILLARS OF DEVELOPING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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Annotation. Today, following a healthy lifestyle has become a very urgent issue. Surrounded by electronic devices, ready-made foods, and easy-to-fix (but immune-suppressing) medications, it seems like a daunting task to exercise and maintain a normal routine.

Key words: healthy lifestyle, proper nutrition, bad habits, daily routine, clean air, personal hygiene, hypodynamia.

ОСНОВНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ

Аннотация. Сегодня здоровый образ жизни стал крайне актуальным. В окружении электронных устройств, готовой еды и легко поддающихся лечению (но подавляющих иммунитет) лекарств заниматься спортом и поддерживать привычный режим кажется непростой задачей.

Ключевые слова: здоровый образ жизни, правильное питание, вредные привычки, режим дня, чистый воздух, личная гигиена, гиподинамия.

Adhering to a healthy lifestyle means preventing many problems. Today we are faced with this topic very often. What are the main rules of a healthy lifestyle, which at first glance seems difficult, requiring a lot of strength, patience and will, time and conditions? How can one adhere to a healthy lifestyle today, when there is no easier task than giving advice to others? The following 7 most important rules of a healthy lifestyle will remind you of the procedures that we have known for a long time, but have forgotten and failed to implement due to the petty worries of life. Sport is one of the main conditions for living a healthy life until the end of our lives. It does not choose age, place, or even conditions. It has many manifestations, forms, and methods.

There are yoga, pilates, walking, running, pulling up a barbell, horsemanship, dancing, rafting, bodybuilding, gymnastics, football, etc. Choose what you like, it is enough if you are physically active. If you do sports for 30-60 minutes every other day, not every day, it is enough to be healthy. You need to sit less and move more. If your profession requires you to work while sitting, take a break for at least 5 minutes every hour and do various light exercises at this time, stretching your shoulders, back and legs.

Proper nutrition. Include more natural products in your diet - fruits and vegetables, foods rich in vitamins and minerals. 65% of the diet should be fruits and vegetables, bread and various cereals, 30% should be meat and dairy products, and 5% should be sweets and fats. Foods should be as fresh as possible, seasonal. In spring and summer, more emphasis should be placed on plants, and in winter on products rich in protein and fat. Drink about 2 liters of water every day.

Avoid fast food, carbonated drinks, semi-finished products, chips and kiriyeshki, and many other foods with artificial flavors, colors and shapes. Do not mix different foods when eating. Fruits should be consumed half an hour before meals, tea and drinks 1-2 hours after. After 7:00 p.m., only a small apple is allowed.

Bad habits. Open the way to a healthy lifestyle by giving up tobacco and alcohol, which are the main enemies of our body, as well as various bad habits (which you know well). Every cigarette not smoked, every glass of vodka not drunk is an important step towards a healthy life.

Daily routine. Strictly adhere to the daily routine. First of all, 8 hours of sleep! Secondly, get used to going to bed at the same time of day and waking up at a certain time!

Sleep disorders gradually harm a person's psyche and emotions, reduce their working capacity, and can later lead to the development of various chronic, serious diseases. Another important rule of a healthy lifestyle is a bright and positive mood! Enjoy life more, do not focus too much on failures and setbacks, always find the strength to move forward and do not hold grudges, resentments, and bad suspicions towards people, be forgiving and tolerant. Never try to be on a par with ignorant people!

Clean air. Always keep your house, room, and office clean, clean it every day, open the windows and ensure fresh air. To be in normal physical condition, you must know how to breathe deeply and correctly. It is not enough to take a walk in nature, leave the windows open for a certain period of time, do physical work in the yard or outdoors.

Personal hygiene. Washing hands before and after eating, brushing teeth before sleeping and after eating, clean clothes, strict adherence to cleanliness in general are the main conditions of a healthy lifestyle.

Do not forget! A healthy lifestyle is a guarantee of health, strength and prevention of any diseases. It is a guarantee of success and development of various aspects of a person. A person who adheres to the rules of a healthy lifestyle will have a place in the family, work team, society in general, learn to overcome various difficult situations and not lose oneself in the face of life's difficulties.

Another word! The rules of a healthy lifestyle support each other, one cannot happen without the other. We will take the first steps towards a healthy and happy life by starting to implement them now, without leaving them for tomorrow. Physical activity and general hygiene of the body, training. Physical activity is the second basic component of healthy lifestyle. A person should always strive to develop physical qualities such as strength, dexterity, speed, endurance. Each of us has many jobs that require physical strength and reliable training. In the process of regular physical exercises, not only health is strengthened, but also a feeling of well-being and mood improves, a sense of freshness and cheerfulness appears. Modern production and life

conditions have greatly reduced human movement activity. According to Academician A.I. Berg (2000), in the last century, muscle energy consumption in production was 94%, and now it is only 1%. Lack of movement has a negative effect on human health. Regular physical education and sports, morning physical education, exercise breaks, walks, tourism are aimed at filling the place of hunger for movement of hypodynamia. This is confirmed by the researches of experts from Stanford University in the USA, American scientists give many ideas that convince people to do physical exercises. Among them, read the following: Exercise is a pleasure There is a suitable type of exercise for everyone After a few months you will be so used to it that you will never be able to quit it After half a year: You will be more active, more energetic. Your strength will increase, the balance of movements will improve, reaction speed will increase, it will be easier to get rid of nervous tension and bad mood. It is impossible not to agree with these conclusions, because they have always been proven in practice. Physical exercise is basically an integral part of a healthy lifestyle, because without physical activity, not only the physical but also the mental condition of a person deteriorates, the intellectual capabilities of a person decrease (doctors say that mental work should be fully compensated by physical work).

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